

POLICY BRIEF

European macroalgae import

382 060 tons
mix of dry weight/semi
dry/fresh weight

mainly in the
phycocolloid
industry → **65-85% of the total algal
biomass is discarded as
waste**

**European algae
production (1.4%)**

European microalgae production

↓
represents **less than 0.5%** of the
global microalgae production

WE NEED TO...

Accelerate and support algae cultivation

Scale-up algae production

Adopt innovative
production models to
enhance algae yield

Simplify licensing & integrate algae cultivation in maritime spatial planning

Make licensing process
faster for offshore, near-
shore and inland seaweed
farms

Enable the cultivation of high-demand species in controlled environment

Support controlled algae
cultivation to meet the
market demand

Showcase ecosystem benefits to improve societal acceptance

Highlight carbon impact,
biodiversity gains and
other benefits of algae
production

Measure environmental, economic and social impacts

Prove algae's role in the
blue economy & circular
bioeconomy

WE NEED TO...

Remove regulatory barriers and harmonize regulatory landscape

Establish a clear, supportive and coherent regulatory framework for microalgae production

- Encourage safe use of secondary input materials in algae production where appropriate
- Utilize cost-effective fertilizers like Nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P) for algae cultivation
- Establish clear regulations for algae grown with secondary inputs or sourced from environmental remediation
- Define the regulatory status of waste-fed algae products

Harmonize and simplify European regulatory framework

Standardize regulations across Europe with clear field-specific guidelines aligned with European laws

Align feed and food safety regulations for contaminants

Define thresholds for harmful substances based on portion size and toxicity

Clarify the definition of novel food ingredients and feed additives

Establish clear purity criteria, differentiate raw vs. extracted products, and streamline authorization processes

Reevaluate testing and assessment requirements

Review toxicological and genotoxicological testing requirements and reassess allergenicity risk assessments, protein quality, and digestibility

WE NEED TO...

Promote acceptability of algae as food or food ingredients

Encourage wider adoption of algae, particularly for food

Increase consumer awareness of the algae's nutritional and environmental benefits in daily diets

Raise public awareness through targeted campaigns

Educate the public on algae's health benefits, sustainability and the role in circular economy

Engage with educational institutions

Collaborate with schools, universities, and vocational programs to create curricula that train a skilled workforce for the algae industry

Support the EU4Algae platform

The platform facilitates collaboration among European algae stakeholders and provides easy access to evidence-based algae informations

Promote the establishment of regional clusters to facilitate the processing of co-products

Facilitate technology transfer from research to industry

Encourage the transfer of innovative technologies from research institutions to industry with licensing agreements and provide support for pilot-scale testing

Build open-access pilot-scale facilities for biorefinery processes

Establish pilot scale biorefinery facilities near co-product resources to support algae processing. These facilities should be designed to benefit all stakeholders

Enhance cooperation through biorefinery cluster

Foster collaboration between companies by creating biorefinery clusters (stabilization and transportation of co-products optimization, local collaborations...)

WE NEED TO...

Boost funding for applied research, development and scale-up

Expand funding and subsidies for the algae industry

Offer financial support to drive growth and innovation in the algae sector

Establish grant programs

Launch targeted grants for research, development, and commercialization of sustainable algae technologies

Support standardization initiatives

Fund industry standardization efforts like the CEN TC 454, ensuring long-term support from DG Mare and DG SANCO

Facilitate matchmaking between business and investors

Create platform that connect algae businesses with potential investors to provide financial backing for innovative algae-based solutions

Create dedicated investment funds

Set up investment funds focused on sustainable algae innovations

CIRCALGAE
Food • Feed • Cosmetic

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